

THE DOMESTICATION OF CEREALS IN THE NEAR EAST

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Résumé : Deux modèles sont actuellement proposés pour décrire la domestication des céréales au Proche-Orient : un modèle de domestication rapide à l'intérieur d'une zone centrale limitée correspondant aux habitats naturels de plusieurs progéniteurs sauvages (Heun *et al.*, 2012), et un modèle de domestication lente à différents endroits (Fuller *et al.*, 2012). Des trouvailles récentes sur Chypre (Vigne *et al.*, 2012) montrent que, dès le PPNA, des céréales sauvages ont été cultivées après leur transplantation loin de l'habitat initial de leurs progéniteurs. Ceci suggère que la domestication des céréales a pu avoir lieu à l'extérieur de la zone centrale. Mais il n'est pas certain que cette culture des céréales sauvages pendant le PPNA ait lentement sélectionné des traits adaptatifs vers la domestication.

Abstract : Two models are currently invoked to describe the domestication of cereals in the Near East : the model of a rapid domestication within a core area corresponding to the natural habitats of several wild progenitors (Heun *et al.*, 2012), and the model of a protracted domestication occurring in different regions (Fuller *et al.*, 2012). Recent findings on Cyprus (Vigne *et al.*, 2012) confirm that, as early as the PPNA, wild cereals have been cultivated after their transplantation far away from the natural habitats of their wild progenitors. This suggests that cereal domestication could have taken place outside the core area. But it is not clear whether or not the cultivation of wild cereals during the PPNA has slowly selected adaptive traits on the way towards domestication.

Mots-clés : domestication des céréales - PPNA - culture - transplantation - rachis résistant.

Keywords : cereal domestication - PPNA - cultivation - transplantation - non-shattering rachis.

Explaining and understanding the processes that led to domestic agriculture has been for a long time, and still is, a major problem in archaeology¹. The Near East is the region where the most ancient domestic agriculture appeared first, and where the important cereals, einkorn (*Triticum monococcum*), emmer (*Triticum dicoccum*) and barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), were domesticated². Despite important recent findings in Near East excavations and major improvements in recovery and identification of plant remains, there are still some conflicting views about where and how did people in the Near East shift their lifestyle from being collectors of wild cereals to become farmers producing domesticated cereals. For instance, in 2012 the *Journal of Experimental Botany* has published two articles with opposite conclusions. For the first one cereal domestication has taken place at multiple centers and over a long period of time³, and for the other cereal domestication has taken place within a defined core region and in a shorter time period⁴. The aim of this paper is to discuss the evidence in favor of one or the other of these proposals.

Distinguishing between wild and domesticated cereals in archaeobotanical remains

Wild cereals have a brittle rachis that shatters spontaneously upon ripening, so that the ears disintegrate and the spikelets fall on the ground for germinating next year. This spontaneous process leaves a smooth abscission scar. In contrast, domesticated cereals have a solid rachis that does not shatter, so that ripe ears remain intact and can be harvested entirely. This solid rachis needs to be broken by threshing, which leaves a rough abscission scar⁵. Most studies have used the presence of a smooth abscission scar as the archaeological marker of cereal domestication⁶.

Another difference between wild and domestic cereals is the size of the grains⁷. However, this criterion is not absolute as the size distributions of wild and domestic cereals show significant overlap. In addition, increase in grain

1 For an update see the recent special issues of *Current Anthropology*, october 2009 and october 2011, and of *Vegetation History and Archaeobotany*, march 2012.

2 Zohary *et al.*, 2012.

3 Fuller *et al.*, 2012.

4 Heun *et al.*, 2012.

5 Tanno et Willcox, 2006 ; Tanno et Willcox, 2012.

6 Brown et al., 2008.

7 Willcox, 2004 ; Fuller, 2007; Puruggannan et Fuller, 2011.

size seems also related to soil management: large grains are favored in tilled soils as they bury deeper, survive better and produce larger seedlings⁸. But soil management does not mean domestication: wild cereals have been «cultivated»⁹ and the sizes of their grains have increased long before they were domesticated (see below pp. 9 -11).

When and where have cereals been domesticated?

Despite the marked difficulty of differentiating wild and domestic cereals in archaeobotanical remains¹⁰, the present consensus is that domesticated cereals with a non-shattering rachis did not appear in southwestern Asia before early PPNB (Pre Pottery Neolithic B), *i.e.* not before 10500 cal BP, as no domestic phenotype of einkorn, emmer or barley, has yet been found at any site from the PPNA (Pre Pottery Neolithic A), 11700-10500 cal BP¹¹.

THE NATURAL HABITATS OF WILD PROGENITORS SUGGESTS A UNIQUE «CORE» REGION FOR CEREAL DOMESTICATION

The naturally growing wild progenitors of domesticated cereals have been identified using both morphological resemblance and molecular genetics: *Triticum boeoticum* for einkorn, *Triticum dicoccoides* for emmer, and *Hordeum spontaneum* for barley¹². Archaeobotanical assemblages coincide with present day distributions, and suggest that past natural habitats of these wild progenitors were similar to present habitats¹³. In the Near East the natural habitats of wild einkorn, emmer and barley overlap each other, so it has been proposed that their domestications took place within a unique «core» region, in the upper valleys of Euphrates and Tigris¹⁴, where all their progenitors were growing naturally. The same core area may also have been the site for the domestication of several legumes¹⁵.

8 Purugganan et Fuller, 2009.

9 The word «cultivation» corresponds to a human intervention aimed at improving either growth only (by tilling, weeding, watering, etc...) or growth and reproduction (by tending the soil and planting/sowing stored seeds).

10 Tanno et Willcox, 2012.

11 Tanno et Willcox, 2012 ; Weiss et Zohary, 2011; Fuller *et al.*, 2012; Willcox, 2012a.

12 Zohary *et al.*, 2012.

13 Willcox 2005 ; Weiss et Zohary, 2011.

14 Lev-Yadun *et al.*, 2000 ; Abbo *et al.*, 2010.

15 Abbo *et al.*, 2009.

COMPARING THE DNAs OF WILD AND DOMESTIC CEREALS

Molecular genetics have also been used to compare the DNAs (DeoxyriboNucleic Acid) from various domestic varieties with those from wild varieties growing in different regions. Cereals are self-fertilizing plants that reproduce locally, so that there is little natural gene flow between widely separated natural habitats¹⁶.

Einkorn. All domestic einkorn varieties are closely related to a wild-type growing on the Karaçadağ hills in southeastern Anatolia, and appear to derive from a monophyletic domestication¹⁷. The unique wild progenitor gave rise to several local wild variants that were later domesticated at different sites¹⁸. However, these separated domestications took place within a limited area well inside of the core region of Lev-Yadun *et al.* (2000). Therefore, even though separated, these domestications can be considered as linked both culturally and genetically.

Emmer. Domestic emmer varieties are close to a wild emmer from the Karaçadağ hills, but some also resemble a wild variety from the south Levant¹⁹. Recent studies have shown that emmer was successfully domesticated only once in southeastern Anatolia, and that some early domesticates were transplanted into south Levant and acquired some genes from local wild varieties²⁰.

Barley. Domestic barley varieties belong to two types, an eastern barley grown in central Asia and far East, and a western barley grown in Europe and America²¹. Such a diphyletic origin suggests (at least) two independent domestication events. The western site of domestication has been located in northeastern Syria²² also within the proposed core area. The second site of barley domestication could be distant of 1 500 to 3 000 km to the east²³, and the two sites would be genetically and culturally independent (see below the note added in proof).

DO PRESENT DOMESTIC CEREALS REVEAL ALL PAST DOMESTICATION EVENTS?

However, even though it fits with molecular genetics, the hypothesis of

¹⁶ Murphy, 2007; Honne et Heun, 2009.

¹⁷ Heun *et al.*, 1997.

¹⁸ Kilian *et al.*, 2007; Heun *et al.*, 2008.

¹⁹ Feldman et Kislev, 2007; Luo *et al.*, 2007.

²⁰ Özkan *et al.*, 2010.

²¹ Azhaguvel et Komatsuda, 2007; Morrell et Clegg, 2007.

²² Russell *et al.*, 2011.

²³ Morrell et Clegg, 2007.

a core area for cereal domestication has been questioned²⁴. It has been first objected that present domestic cultivars do not represent all past domestication events. Some lineages domesticated in the past could have been lost, abandoned, or replaced since then²⁵. Second, *in silico* simulations of evolving populations have suggested that multiple domestication events might yield an apparent monophyletic descent²⁶, which casts some doubt about a unique core area. Third, it is probable that wild cereals were cultivated before their domestication, but outside the core area (see below).

Wild cereals were cultivated long before their domestication

Cultivation of wild cereals has been invoked to account for their intensive use on sites that have environments not favorable to their large production²⁷. Such intensive use is indicated by finding large amounts of cereal remains, abundant traces of cereal chaff as tempering material for building earth, specific harvesting and processing tools, and/or the presence of large (collective ?) cereal storage structures²⁸. Cultivation of wild cereals before their domestication is also indicated by the adventice weeds contaminating wild cereal remains²⁹ and by the increase in cereal grain size³⁰ at several PPNA sites.

The middle Euphrates PPNA sites are quite remote from the natural habitats of wild einkorn and wild rye³¹, which suggests that wild cereals could have been transplanted and cultivated in new habitats. Such transplantation has recently been confirmed by finding that wild emmer was used at the PPNA site of Klimonas in Cyprus³², even though Cyprus is outside the natural habitat of wild emmer³³.

Therefore, as early as the PPNA and before the emergence of the non-shattering rachis domestic phenotype, humans knew how to control the complete reproductive cycle of wild cereals and to transplant them into new territories.

The earlier proposal that cultivation of cereals could have started during

24 Fuller *et al.*, 2011.

25 Gross et Olsen, 2010; Fuller *et al.*, 2012; but see also Abbo *et al.*, 2013.

26 Allaby *et al.*, 2008; Allaby *et al.*, 2010, but see also Olsen et Gross, 2008; Honne et Heun, 2009.

27 Weiss *et al.*, 2006; Fuller, 2007; Willcox *et al.*, 2008; Bannelier, 2009; Willcox *et al.*, 2009; Fuller *et al.*, 2010; Willcox, 2012a.

28 Weiss *et al.*, 2006; Savard *et al.*, 2006; Kuijt, 2008; Kuijt et Finlayson, 2009; Goodale *et al.*, 2010; Finlayson *et al.*, 2011; Vigne *et al.*, 2012; Willcox et Stordeur, 2012.

29 Willcox *et al.*, 2008; Willcox, 2012b.

30 Willcox, 2004; Purugganan et Fuller, 2011; Riehl *et al.*, 2012.

31 Willcox, 2005; Willcox *et al.*, 2008; Willcox, 2012a; Willcox et Stordeur, 2012.

32 Vigne *et al.*, 2012.

33 Willcox, 2005; Weiss et Zohary, 2011 ; Zohary *et al.*, 2012.

Younger Dryas³⁴ is still under discussion, and most scholars agree that cultivation on a wide scale began only after the onset of Holocene³⁵. For instance, paleoclimate reconstruction shows that wild einkorn could not grow on the Karaçadağ hills during the Younger Dryas³⁶. Therefore large-scale cereal cultivation has started only after the termination of the Younger Dryas and not before the beginning of PPNA, around 11700-11500 cal BP, *i.e.* some 1000 years before domestication.

Was cereal domestication a rapid or a protracted process?

There is a consensus that wild cereals were cultivated well before their domestication, but some discussions remain about whether or not this long cultivation phase of the PPNA has been a pre-domestication step with the first genetic changes towards domestication. Two models for cereal domestication are currently proposed.

The first model considers that domestication took place rapidly within a restricted core region, and that the preceding cultivation phase did not exert any selective pressure³⁷. This model is supported by the biogeography of wild progenitors (see p. 7), the DNA comparison between wild and domestic varieties (see p. 8), and field experiments which have indicated that a strong recurrent selection could domesticate wild cereals within a time as short as 20 to 100 years³⁸. Some possible criticisms of this model have already been outlined above (see p. 8).

The other model considers that domestication was a slow process in which wild cereals were domesticated at multiple centers after a long period of cultivation that had already selected some genetic changes on the way to domestication³⁹. The finding that wild cereals were cultivated outside their zone of natural growth (see p. 9) is in agreement with multiple domestication sites⁴⁰. The tenants of this protracted model observe continuous and linear increases with time of both grain size and fraction of non-shattering rachis over a 4000 years period

34 Hillman *et al.*, 2001.

35 Willcox *et al.*, 2009; Colledge and Conolly, 2010; Bar-Yosef, 2011.

36 Haldorsen *et al.*, 2011.

37 Abbo *et al.*, 2010; Abbo *et al.*, 2012; Heun *et al.*, 2012.

38 Hillmann et Davis, 1990.

39 Fuller, 2007; Purugganan et Fuller, 2009; Allaby *et al.*, 2008; Allaby, 2010; Fuller *et al.*, 2012.

40 Fuller *et al.*, 2012.

overlapping domestication, and attribute these increases to a long selective adaptation to an environment modified by human activities⁴¹. But the increase in grain size could be due (at least in part) to better soil management and improved growth conditions⁴². Also, the fraction of non-shattering rachis found at distant sites is a good index of the fixation of this trait⁴³ only if a genetic equilibrium has been reached between all these sites, which could be questioned⁴⁴. Indeed, a slow spontaneous gene flow of self-fertilizing cereals could be masked by a fast efficient human-borne dispersion of wild and/or domestic cereals⁴⁵.

Presently, it is difficult to favor one or the other model, and further evidence is needed to discriminate between the protracted model that places transplantation before domestication and the core area model that places domestication before transplantation.

Possible selection exerted on wild cereals by agronomic methods

Independently of whether the genetic changes associated with cereal domestication have taken place rapidly or slowly, the emergence of the archaeological marker of domestication, the non-shattering rachis, has often been attributed to a selection (conscious or unconscious) by some agronomic practices of cultivation⁴⁶. Such selection begins when seeds for the next harvest have a more solid rachis than the previous generation. Different harvesting methods will select for different traits. Harvesting by cutting the stems with sickles or knives will discriminate between the grains already fallen on the ground with a more labile rachis, and the grains remaining on the stems with a more solid rachis⁴⁷. Harvesting by beating the ears into a basket or by ground collection⁴⁸ will discriminate between the collected grains with a more labile rachis and the remaining grains with a more solid rachis.

Harvesting entire ears well before ripening will not select for any trait of the rachis. But harvesting with sickles at mid-ripening will select for more solid

41 Purugganan et Fuller, 2011; Fuller *et al.*, 2012.

42 Willcox 2005; Fuller, 2007.

43 Tanno et Willcox, 2006; Fuller, 2007 ; Allaby *et al.*, 2008 ; Fuller *et al.*, 2012.

44 Honne et Heun, 2009; Heun *et al.*, 2012.

45 Heun *et al.*, 2012.

46 Hillman et Davis, 1990; Kislev *et al.*, 2004; Bannelier, 2009; Fuller *et al.*, 2010.

47 Hillmann et Davis, 1990.

48 Kislev *et al.*, 2004.

rachis for the collected grains, and for more labile rachis for the fallen grains⁴⁹. A non-shattering rachis is a clear advantage for harvesting entire ears when ripe, but it is also a drawback requiring the extra work of threshing and winnowing to recover the grains from the ears⁵⁰.

C onclusions

Cereal domestication has been a landmark in human history. In the Near East the non-shattering phenotype does not emerge before 10500 cal BP, in the early/middle PPNB, after a long period of cultivation of wild cereals for (at least) 1000 years.

The core area corresponding to the overlap between the natural habitats of einkorn, emmer and western barley⁵¹ includes the mid-Euphrates sites, but not Cyprus⁵². The finding that wild emmer wheat was cultivated at Klimonas during the PPNA⁵³ is very suggestive of a human-borne transplantation outside its zone of natural growth. Such transplantation would have resulted in the genetic isolation of cultivated varieties and prevented gene crossing with neighbouring wild species. Indeed, selection by progressive enrichment of a recessive non-shattering rachis could have been easier in the absence of gene flow between cultivated cereals and their dominant wild relatives growing nearby. It is therefore possible that domestication *per se* has occurred on the margins of or even outside the «core» area, after transplantation.

It has been argued that cultivation of wild cereals was more costly in caloric return per hour of work than foraging them from their natural stands⁵⁴, and that productivity alone could not explain why the first farmers initiated cultivation⁵⁵. But the transplantation of wild cereals outside their zone of natural growth left no choice but to cultivate them, thus eliminating the economic dilemma between cultivating and foraging.

The question that remains open is whether or not cultivation during the PPNA was a pre-domestication. This does not seem to be the case for einkorn⁵⁶.

49 Fuller *et al.*, 2010 ; White et Makarewicz, 2012.

50 Fuller *et al.*, 2010.

51 Lev-Yadun *et al.*, 2000; Abbo *et al.*, 2010.

52 Willcox, 2005; Weiss et Zohary, 2011.

53 Vigne *et al.*, 2012.

54 Bowles, 2011.

55 Barker, 2011; Bowles, 2011.

56 Heun *et al.*, 2012.

The results of both molecular genetics and paleoclimate reconstruction indicate that wild einkorn returned to the Karaçadağ hills in early Holocene⁵⁷, then spread as wild local variants which were later domesticated rapidly and separately⁵⁸. This indicates that human-borne transplantation of a wild progenitor can result in a monophyletic descent after domestication at multiple sites.

For other cereals it is difficult to conclude whether or not cultivation during the PPNA has modified only their phenotype or also their genotype, as it is not clear that the changes in grain size and fraction of non-shattering rachis reveal a true evolutive process⁵⁹ (see p. 10). Improvements in recovery and assignments of plant remains, together with excavations at other outside the core area may relieve this ambiguity (see below the note added in proof).

Independently of any genetic change in wild cereals during the cultivation phase, the recent results obtained about their exploitation in the Near East show that the PPNA has seen the development of an agricultural economy and the beginning of a farming society⁶⁰.

Note added in proof:

Since the submission of this manuscript, the issue of *Science* dated July 5, 2013 released both a research paper by Riehl *et al.* and a comment by Willcox on the beginning of agriculture at the iranian site of Chogha Golan, located at the eastern tip of the Fertile Crescent. This site has revealed an extended sequence of cereal exploitation which covers the transition from wild to domestic cereals and shows that:

- (i) cereals have been intensively exploited over a much larger area than previously thought, notably over the eastern part of the Fertile Crescent;
- (ii) wild cereals were cultivated, and their cultivation began after the Younger Dryas, *i.e.* at about the same time as at other Near East sites;
- (iii) the first domestic cereals appeared around 9800 cal BP, *i.e.* somewhat later (by 700 years) than in the western part of the Fertile Crescent, so that no conclusion can be drawn about whether domestic cereals appeared locally or were imported from western sites;

57 Haldorsen *et al.*, 2011.

58 Kilian *et al.*, 2007 ; Heun *et al.*, 2008.

59 Purugganan *et Fuller*, 2011; Fuller *et al.*, 2012.

60 Bar-Yosef, 2011.

(iv) a wheat type with no modern counterpart was found at several levels, suggesting that present cereals do not reflect all the types exploited in the past.

Chogha Golan is located outside the «core» area of Lev-Yadun *et al.* (2000), but is still within the zones of natural growth of wild einkorn, emmer and barley given by Zohary *et al.* (2012), so that, contrary to the Cyprus site, it does not reveal any transplantation of wild cereals. Therefore these recent results suggest that the eastern part of the Fertile Crescent, which played a critical role in the domestication of animals, could also have played some role in the cultivation and domestication of plants, notably of eastern barley.

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